

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING LITERARY TRANSLATION IN
TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The article deals with the importance of using literary translation in teaching the Russian language. On the other hand, specific features of translation and role of culture in literary translation were discussed.

Key words: *language limitations, institutionalized domains, word-for-word translation, discursive translation, real-world context, language proficiency, drill-and-kill activities.*

Translating or transforming requires good interpretation skills, especially when we refer to institutional discourses. Limitations are sometimes given by the translator's abilities, or by the language limitations. Considering the many types of contexts that can produce communication, and the many types of discourses, the translator must possess solid knowledge about the domain, language, subject, and culture and must know how to transfer all these into meaningful productions that are as true to the original form as possible. Also, a good understanding of linguistic features should add to the translator's ability to deal with many institutionalized domains and endless occurrences when word-for-word translation must be avoided as not securing accuracy, naturalness, and fluency. If discourse is seen as language in practice, then the translator's work is to perceive the limitations that institutional discourses might show and adopt the adequate translation method and procedures, when meeting the institutional needs, to fulfil the task: creating a comprehensible

discursive translation that reads as an original. As it is known, the main purpose of translation lectures is to enrich the word treasure of students with new words and expressions. On the other hand, translation helps to develop the predisposition of students to the foreign language.

For the past several decades, translation and interpreting have been largely excluded from the communicative language classroom—and not without reason. In traditional foreign language classrooms, “literal” or close translation was often used as a comprehension check or as part of a vocabulary or grammar drill, divorced from real-world context. This in turn encouraged students (and, on some rare occasions, foreign language teachers) to view language proficiency—and, by extension, translation competence—as a kind of linguistic matching game. In Hans Vermeer’s terms, bilinguals were believed to merely “transpose” the words of one language into another, which essentially equated translators and interpreters with walking dictionaries. This idea of translation was only strengthened by the rapid rise over the past twenty five years of machine translation tools, such as Google Translate, Babelfish, and Bing Translator, which, for some, obviate the need for proficiency in a foreign language altogether. Correspondingly, when the behaviorist models that generated the now-infamous drill-and-kill activities were replaced by communicative and immersive approaches to language teaching, translation—viewed as undermining the principles of those approaches—was largely from the curriculum[1].

Generally, it is not possible to correct and uniform translation without being adapted to the original language deeply and without being cognized the genuine national entirely. There are some differences of esthetic translation from other translations. The most important difference is style. The feature of esthetic style is to carry the aim of preserving moral purity and entrust translation apart from its esthetic mission. In literary translation, it is not sufficient to know only the foreign language. Here, special artifice, we can even say that having the ability of writing

talent, being noble artists, to know the format of language and word and to give the esthetic characters realistically needed. Furthermore, it should be noted that before comparative translating from the parts of the work, the words and expressions which exist in the text are separately selected and their meanings are broadly given to students[2]. From this point of view, we can give the following word and expression as an example:

- гнать в шею (dismiss);
- деньги листопадом (a blank cheque);
- ломавая музыка (heavy music);
- масскультура (mass culture);
- просить подаяния (begging);
- прямой эфир (live);
- свежая дичь (fresh wildfowl);
- судьбоносный момент (faithfull moment);
- требовать мзду (demanding bribes);
- уличные торжищи (street trade);
- умыкать женщину (kidnapping a women);

Cultural ability in text-based translation is very important in terms of translating some words and phrases that do not exist in the translator's native language, and are known as culture-specific items. Thus, the translator will choose a few relevant translation procedures which could be said to count as creating alterations of the original text. For instance, transfers or borrowings are used to render what cannot normally be rendered in the target language, either because there are no direct equivalents, or the meaning cannot be easily inferred from the word-to-word translation. It is commonly stated that if the translator displays sufficient linguistic, encyclopaedic and cultural competence, he/she will also have transfer competence, "an ability of transferring a message from source text to target text communicatively"[3], that is why it has been claimed that instead of

translating, linguists should use the term "transferring" since the "translator explains how certain language users say or express a certain phenomenon" is of the opinion that the translation process includes a minimum of two stages: understanding the supplied text and choosing a translation variant. These steps showcase the transition from the source text to the target text. Translators typically do not notice what has guided them through the method and made them opt for a specific variant, and their actions are often intuition-driven. This, however, does not mean that the selection is completely random or accidental. It is determined, to an oversized extent, by the mechanisms used to produce a message within the source and target languages. Translation production and evaluation are delimited by "the customer and the cultural factors". If there is not enough documentation, there will be misinterpretations, as "the cultural factor in translation is a set of background conditions whereas the institution is an actor in the translation process". Mossop agrees that the translator must not address the entire culture; nonetheless, he or she must comply with the group's collective culture and address a particular readership[4].

Institutional translation nowadays has become more complex since it covers many fields or, to put it in other words, it is fuzzy at the edges. Due to the multitude of languages and areas to which they can be applied, this type of translation depends largely on "disciplines", having to do with the terms used in certain fields, where the translator needs to keep the original sense without "distorting it"[3]. A translation model is viewed as a tentative description of a sequence of cognitive and metacognitive operations that a translator performs to translate the supplied text in full or partially. A linguistic model of translation methods describes them as a sequence of source text transformations that ought to theoretically produce the required result and a similar effect on the target text readership. Any translation model is theoretical since there is no evidence that a translator acts specifically as the model suggests[4]. Translations should,

nonetheless, replace the text without changing the form (unless required to do so by the client), rendering the same meaning as in the original form.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that translation plays an important role in increasing awareness and understanding among diverse cultures and nations. Literary translations in particular help these different cultures reach a compromise. The increasing interest in the literature of other languages has required a more studious regard for the problems of literary translation. A translator deals with a text which involves linguistic, pragmatic and cultural elements. Such factors often pose problems to target readers. Literal translation is generally said to be wrong but this judgment is not always right because whether literal translation is right or wrong depends on the objective of the translation: it is wrong if the objective is to give the equivalent in the TL of a text written in the SL and it may be right if the objective is, for example, to show whether there are grammatical differences, including differences in word order, between two languages when conveying the same meaning or communication, but then, the literal translation is expected to be followed by the 'faithful translation'. Translation is an important phenomenon in increasing awareness and understanding among various cultures as well as nations. So, literary translations, in particular, help these different cultures reach a compromise. The increasing interest in the literature of other languages has required a more studious regard for the problems of literary translation.

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